

ROSIE

D8.3: Release of the 1st promotional video

Authors: Panagiotis Kavouras

Editors: Søren Holm

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Editor(s):	Søren Holm
Contributor(s):	Panagiotis Kavouras
Reviewer(s):	Rosemarie de La Cruz Bernabe
Approved by	Søren Holm

Consortium:

No.	Role	Name	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	ÖSTERREICHISCHE AGENTUR FÜR WISSENSCHAFTLICHE INTEGRITÄT	OeAWI	Austria
3.	Partner	VEREIN DER EUROPÄISCHEN BÜRGERWISSENSCHAFTEN	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	EUREC OFFICE GUG	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	TIETEELLISTEN SEURAINVALTUUSKUNNASTA	TSV	Finland
6.	Partner	HAUT CONSEIL DE L'EVALUATION DE LA RECHERCHE ET DE L'ENSEIGNEMENT SUPERIEUR	HCERES	France
7.	Partner	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE	France
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9.	Partner	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA	UCP	Portugal
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11.	Partner	TARTU ULIKOOL	UT	Estonia
12.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	Norway

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	17 Nov 2021	Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the script
0.2	26 Nov 2021	Panagiotis Kavouras	Preparation of the 1 st draft of the voice over
0.3	2 Dec 2021	Rose Bernabe, Søren Holm	Comments on the 1 st draft of the voice over
0.4	15 Dec 2021	NTUA team	Recording of the voice over
0.5	21 Dec 2021	NTUA team	Preparation of the scenes – basic aesthetic elements
0.6	20 Feb 2022	NTUA team	Preparation of the first version of the video
0.7	14 Mar 2022	Rose Bernabe, Søren Holm	Comments of the first version of the video
1.0	20 Mar 2022	NTUA team	Preparation of the final version

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1 Aim of the 1st promotional video

The 1st promotional video of ROSiE aims to present a summary of the project for communication purposes. It mainly targets non-expert audience and captures all basic elements of ROSiE through animated pictures and cartoons.

2 The script of the video

This section presents the video by showcasing the voice over and some characteristic screen captures from the animations.

Scene	Narration	Visual
1.	No voice over (Introduction of ROSiE acronym and logo)	The visual content of the table cell shows a screenshot of the ROSiE logo. The logo consists of two overlapping red speech bubble shapes. The top bubble is partially behind the bottom one, and they overlap in the center. Below the speech bubbles, the word "ROSiE" is written in a bold, red, sans-serif font. The background of the screenshot is a light gray gradient.

<p>2. No voice over (Acknowledgement of our funders)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Introduction to the ROSiE project</p> <p style="text-align: center;">The project leading to this application has received funding from the grant the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101006430.</p>
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3. ROSIE stands for **Responsible Open Science in Europe**. It is a Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action that aims at the development and free sharing of practical tools that ensure research ethics and research integrity in open science and citizen science, by involving all relevant stakeholders into a wide consultation and co-creation activity.

4. For such an ambitious set of aims to be met, ROSIE brings together a multi-national and transdisciplinary consortium that coordinated by the Oslo University. This consortium is composed of twelve research performing organizations that come from ten different European countries.

<p>5. The operationalisation of responsible open science and citizen science will be made possible through the ROSIE Knowledge Hub that will be built to provide customized solutions to all interested stakeholders that aspire to actively pursue open approaches in science and research, while complying with relevant legal frameworks, ethical standards, and best practices.</p>	
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6. But what do we mean by “responsible” Open Science? We mean that the opening of data should be made in such a way that is fully aligned to the General Data Protection Rule, while providing safeguards for the integrity of the opened data.

7. The ROSiE Knowledge Hub will compile all existing resources that will be mapped from ROSiE and integrate all inputs that will be provided by stakeholders during the project's engagement processes.

<p>8. ROSiE activities fall into four distinct but interpenetrating and organically interacting cornerstones:</p>	<p>The diagram consists of a light gray rectangular background. Centered horizontally within this background are four red speech bubble shapes, each containing a white word. From left to right, the words are: EXPLORE, GUIDE, ENGAGE, and EQUIP. Each speech bubble has a small tail pointing downwards and slightly to the right.</p>
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9. **EXPLORE:** A systematic inventory of Research Ethics, Research Integrity, social, and legal implications and challenges of Open Science will be compiled, while scanning of existing technologies and platforms that safeguard responsible Open Science will be made.

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10 **GUIDE:** ROSiE will promote responsible Open Science, by providing a set of guiding outputs: Operational guidelines for relevant stakeholders, a supplement to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity within the Open Science framework, and guidance on existing technologies and platforms for responsible Open Science.

11 **ENGAGE:** ROSiE will run, throughout its duration, a wide consultation and stakeholder engagement exercise. The ambition is to create and facilitate a community of practice to gather knowledge on Research Ethics and Integrity in Open Science from other European projects.

12 **EQUIP:** ROSiE will equip all interested stakeholders with a Research Ethics and Integrity Knowledge Hub for Open Science and with training materials for Research Ethics and Integrity aspects of Open Science.

13 The ROSiE Knowledge Hub will provide not only generic recommendations, but also a degree of parametrization with regard to disciplinary focus, level of citizen science involvement, prevalent types of data, and number of involved users in research projects and initiatives.

14 A set of optimized solutions will be freely provided to be integrated in the service layers of existing Open Science platforms. ROSIE will provide a rationale why a specific technology should be selected in preference to another, how Open Science infrastructures should be designed, and how to organize and manage different solutions.


```
<
int i;
unsigned int count = group_info->ngroups;

for (i = 0; i < group_info->nblocks; i++) {
    unsigned int cp_count = min(NGROUPS_PER_BLOCK, count);
    unsigned int len = cp_count * sizeof(*grouplist);

    if (copy_from_user(group_info->blocks[i], grouplist, len)

```


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15 Stay tuned on the progress of the ROSiE project by following us through our Twitter and LinkedIn account, and by visiting the ROSiE website.

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twitter.com/rosie_open

ROSIE

rosie-project.eu

3 Communication of the 1st promotional video

The 1st promotional video will be communicated through the front page of the project's website, through ROSiE's social media channels, and it will be an element to be integrated in presentation in conferences, cluster meetings of EU-funded projects, meetings of European networks, and in any other occasion that demands the presentation of an overall summary of ROSiE for non-experts.

4 Deviations from DoA

D8.3 was delivered three weeks after the deadline. This delay was caused from the fact that the main designer was hospitalised due to COVID-19. This delay did not cause any negative side effects to the implementation of WP8 or ROSiE project at large.

